

AN ECONOMIC AND SPORTS PERFORMANCE RELATIONSHIP IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to find out the relationship between investment of finance and sports performance in India. The study was conducted in the period 2012 to 2016 that includes seasons 2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015 and 2015-2016. The sources of collecting data was various governing body of games and sports in India; their official websites i.e. IOC, IOA, OCA, government website of finance and Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports. Only the achievement in international games & sports like winner in any tournament and gold, silver and bronze medallists in any discipline was considered as achievement in game and sports and taken into consideration in this study. Year wise games and sports budgeting which is officially announced by finance minister of India in every years was taken into consideration. Total number of international events which were occurred in each year taken as a variable of this study. The mean and standard deviation of the variables were employed as a descriptive statistic. A Pearson Product Moment correlation was employed to see the correlation among the variables by setting 0.05 level of significance. The result was expelled significance between sports performance and the years. A linear positive correlation was found between sports performance and the Years.

Key Words: Sports Finance, Sports Performance, Finance Investment, Medallists.

INTRODUCTION

Some countries win lots of medal and achieved highest while others win very less and show lower category in sports. Is there economy has any relationship with sports performance? Research conducted internationally to identify factors that affect sports performance focuses on resource endowments, a country's population, cultural

and social resources (Kiviahho and Makela 1978; Bernard and Busse 2004; Andreff, 2001; Johnson and Ali 2004). It is suggested that countries those are successful in sports have an abundance of financial resources, have a large population and an appropriate climate. The studies tend to suggest that countries such as the United States, Great Britain, and Australia have an advantage in sports competitions due to their economic endowments. The research fails to explain why poor countries are able often to compete successfully despite these apparent obstacles. For instance, Kenya and Ethiopia excel in middle distance running, Angola in basketball, and the Cameroon in football. Yet, South Africa, with its economic hegemony on the continent, underperforms relative to its economic endowment. The majority of scholars were researched to find out the connection between the sporting success of a country measured by the number of medals won at international competitions (mostly Olympic Games) and numerous economic, but also sociological and political variables (Jokl and associates, 1956; Johnson and Ali, 2000, 2004; Moosa and Smith, 2004; Lui and Suen, 2008). The most commonly used variables are GDP per capita, hosting the competition, political system of a country, population, climate etc. (Čustonja and Škorić, 2011). All the results are based on econometric testing, mostly regression analysis, and find that GDP or GDP per capita and population are significant determinants of Olympic performances (Andreff, 2008:5).

It can be argued that a country's success in sport should be evaluated relative to its economic resources. The purpose of this study is to find out the relationship between economy and sports performance and analysing sports performance in relation to economic resources in India.

METHODS

The study was conducted in the period 2012 to 2016 that includes seasons 2011-2012, 2012-2013, 2013-2014, 2014-2015 and 2015-2016. To collect the data the websites of various governing body of games and sports in India;

their official websites i.e. IOC, IOA, OCA, government website of finance and Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports were searched. Only the achievement in international games & sports like champion in any tournament or gold, silver and bronze medallists in any discipline was considered as achievement in game and sports and taken into consideration in this study. One point was given equally for winning a tournament or achieving gold, silver and bronze medals in any games and sports. Year wise games and sports budgeting which is officially announced by finance minister of India in every years was taken into consideration as invested finance for games and sports. Another variable of the study was number of international sports events held in each year. A year wise list of games and sports, number of medals, investment of finance and their mean and standard deviation was illustrated as descriptive statistic. Pearson Product Moment correlation was conducted to find of the relationship among Sports Event, invested finance and sports performance within this five years. A level of significance was taken 0.05.

RESULTS

The results of five year data of the achievements of country in various sports was obtained and is shown in the Table-1.

Table - 1
Year wise Achievement in Various Games & Sports

Name of the Games & Sports	'12	'13	'14	'15	'16	Total
Shooting	2	9	27	5	50	93
wrestling	7	9	24	9	28	77
Badminton	1	1	10	12	16	40
Boxing	5	5	14	12	11	47
Judo	14	8	37	5	12	76
Kabaddi	2	1	6	0	13	22
Football	1	2	1	1	4	9
Cricket	6	6	8	6	4	30
Hockey	2	3	3	2	5	15
Basketball	2	0	3	1	1	7
Volleyball	0	0	1	0	2	3
Handball	0	0	0	0	2	2
Tennis	3	2	6	9	12	32
Table Tennis	14	16	6	10	12	58
Rowing	3	0	3	0	0	6
Track & Field	1	17	16	36	18	88
Aquatics	0	0	1	1	45	47
Squash	0	0	8	2	5	15
Gymnastic	0	0	1	0	55	56
Weight lifting & Best Physique	3	14	18	43	66	144

Archery	0	0	5	3	14	22
Wushu	0	12	5	25	16	58
Sailing	0	0	1	0	0	1
Beach Sepaktakraw	0	0	2	0	0	2
Kurash	0	0	1	1	1	3
Muaythai	0	0	1	0	0	1
Martial Arts	0	10	0	0	2	12
Cycling	0	0	0	0	13	13
Kho-kho	1	0	0	0	2	3
Taekwondo	0	0	0	0	10	10
Triathlon	0	0	0	2	6	8
Sum of performance	67	115	208	185	425	1000

Tabl-1 shows the year wise achievements in various games and sports the data reveals that the Country has performed well at International competitions in Shooting (93 medals), Wrestling (77 Medals) and Judo (76 Medals) . There is considerable performance in Hockey (15) and Cricket (30) has improved as compared to past four years.

Table – 2
Year Wise Comparative Chart of Total Number of Events, Performance and Finance

The Federal Government and MYAS provide a budgetary allocation for sports activities each year. However, much of this money does not produce the intended results in terms of the number of medals won by the country in international and regional sporting events.

Year	Events	Performance	Finance (In crores)
2012	22	67	288.00
2013	29	115	302.00
2014	24	208	326.00
2015	29	185	405.00
2016	22	425	369.00

Source: Rajya Sabha Unstarred Question No. 3096, dated on 20.12.2012; Lok Sabha Starred Question No. 556, dated on 06.05.2013; Lok Sabha Unstarred Question No. 2935, dated on 10.02.2014; and Lok Sabha Starred Question No. 29, dated on 08.07.2014.

Table – 3
Descriptive Statistics of Selected Variables

Variables	N	Mean	SD
Performance	5	200.0000	137.68442
Finance	5	3.3800E9	4.84510E8
Events	5	25.2000	3.56371

Note: Here N = Number of years = 5

Table no. 3 shows the means and standard deviations of the selected variables. The mean along with SD of Performance, Finance and

Events were 200.0000 ± 137.68442 , $3.3800E9 \pm 4.84510E8$, 25.2000 ± 3.56371 respectively.

Table – 4
Pearson Product Moment Correlation
among Selected Variables

S. No	Variable I	Variable II	N	Pearson Correlation	P Value
1	Performance	Year	5	.903*	.036
2	Finance	Year	5	.865	.058
3	Event	Year	5	.000	1.000
4	Performance	Finance	5	.584	.301
5	Performance	Event	5	-.349	.565
6	Finance	Event	5	.279	.649

*Significance at 0.05 level.

Table number 4 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation among the selected variables with their P values and sample size. The Performance was found to be positively significantly correlated (.903) with the Year and the Finance was found positively correlated (.814) with the Year but not significance. The variable Event was found to be positively correlated (.000) with Year and there was positive correlation between Performance and Finance was also found positively correlated (.532) with the Finance but not significance. The Performance was found negatively correlated (-.349) with Event and the Finance was found positively correlated (.277) with Event but not significance.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

India's performance in international sporting events saw a progress since 2000 following the launch of the MYAS. However, most events in which Indian sportsperson earned recognition were individual events for which the training was personalised to them. The culture of sports in India witnessed a sudden boost through the model of Indian Premier League (IPL) introduced in cricket. The model saw the formation of various leagues owned by private individuals and collectives sponsoring and buying players for the event. Cricket was modified from its existing format to suit this business proposal. As per the medal tally it is shown in Table-1. India has won major international medals in Shooting (93), Badminton (40), Wrestling

(77) and Boxing (47) these sports shows that they are the potential sports for Medal prospects for India.

Further the study has shown positive correlation between Finance and increased fund on the performance at International Level.

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